

A METHOD FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF LACTONES OF SUBSTITUTED CROTONIC ACIDS. CONDENSATION OF β -ARYL GLUTACONIC ANHYDRIDES WITH PHENOLIC ETHERS

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A general method for the synthesis of various lactones of substituted crotonic acids has been worked out by the condensation of β -aryl substituted glutaconic anhydrides with phenolic ethers in the presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$. The corresponding lactones in the case of *8*-(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride and (i) anisole, (ii) *o*-cresol methyl ether and (iii) thymol methyl ether have been obtained in good yield. This type of lactones might be expected to have good anthelmintic properties.

Santonin possesses vermifugal properties, which have been attributed to the presence of a "lactonic ring" in the substance. The property was also shown to be possessed by various other substituted lactones (Trendelenburg, *Arch. Exp. Path. & Pharm.*, 1916, 79; Oettingen, *J. Pharm. Exp. Therp.*, 1929, 36, 335; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2025; Rosenmund and Shapiro, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, 272, 313).

Nargund and co-workers (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1940, 9, III, 145; 1941, 10, III, 99; 1942, 11, 124; 1943, 11A, 104; *Rasayanam*, 1943, 1, 233; *Porc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 19A, 381; *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1944, 13, 22) prepared substituted butyrolactones some of which they claim to have superior anthelmintic properties. They have obtained these lactones starting with the condensation of aryl-substituted succinic anhydrides with phenolic ethers.

The β -aryl glutaconic anhydrides (Limaye and Bhave, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 137; Limaye and Gogte, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1934, 3, III, 135; Dixit and Gokhale, *ibid.*, 1934, 3, III, 80; Bhave, Ph. D. Thesis, Univ. Bom., 1942) differ from the aryl substituted succinic anhydrides only by one CH_2 group and a double bond.

These β -aryl glutaconic anhydrides were therefore expected to give the corresponding crotonic acids and the lactones as observed by Bhave (*Rasayanam*, 1941, Nov. 6).

where R = C₆H₄OCH₃ group
(4-methoxyphenyl)

Gogte, however, had reported that such a reaction did not take place in the case of *p*-cresol ethyl ether and β -(2-ethoxy-5-methylphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, **2A**, 185). He attributed the failure to the presence of unsaturation in the side-chain of the glutaconic anhydride.

In view of these conflicting observations it was thought necessary to confirm the structures of the above products of condensation (Bhave, *loc. cit.*).

The Lactone of β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)- γ -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-crotonic Acid

This lactone (A, m. p. 174°) was prepared by condensing the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride with anisole in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃. It was also accompanied with a small quantity of the corresponding acid (B), m. p. 132°.

The structure of the lactone and the acid were confirmed as follows :

(1) The lactone (A, m. p. 174°; C₁₉H₁₈O₄) could be converted into the acid (B, m. p. 132°; C₁₉H₁₈O₅) by the action of alcoholic alkali and the acid (B) into the lactone (A) by the action of acetic anhydride or mineral acids.

(2) On decarboxylation the acid (B) gave a ketone (C), m. p. 97°, C₁₈H₁₈O₃.

(3) On oxidation the acid (B) as also the ketone (C) gave only *anisic acid*.

(4) The acid (B) gave a high melting (above 300°), brightly coloured pyrylium derivative showing the presence of a COCH₂-group (Decker and Fellenburg, *Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 302; Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 1085; Dalal, Bokil and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1939, **8**, III, 190).

(5) On reduction the acid (B) took up two hydrogen atoms to give a ketonic acid (D, m. p. 125°; C₁₉H₂₀O₅) from which the usual ketonic derivatives were prepared.

(6) The structure of the acid (D, m. p. 125°) was further confirmed by preparing it by condensing the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride with anisole.

On the basis of the foregoing evidence the structures of the acid (B) and the lactone (A) must be represented by (I) and (II) above respectively *i.e.*, (A) is the lactone of the acid (B) which is β -(4-methoxyphenyl)- γ -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-crotonic acid, which thus confirms the structures, provisionally assigned to them by Bhave (*loc. cit.*).

The above reaction between β -aryl glutaconic anhydrides and phenolic ethers has been found to be of general and wide application and the extension of the reaction to the condensation of β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride with *o*-cresol methyl ether and thymol methyl ether has also been carried out with similar results.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1) *Lactone of β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)- γ -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-crotonic Acid.*— β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride (2.18 g.) and anisole (1.08 g.) were dissolved in distilled

nitrobenzene (10 c. c.) and freshly powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (3 g.) was slowly added. After 4 hours it was poured into about 80 c. c. of cold water and 10 c. c. of conc. HCl . The nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation. The reaction product was washed first with water and then rubbed in a mortar with dilute solutions of Na_2CO_3 and NaOH and again with water. [These alkaline washings on acidification with dil. HCl gave a small amount (0.150 g.) of the acid of m. p. 132° , described below.] The solid remaining behind was dried and crystallised from alcohol in lemon-yellow crystals, m. p. 174° , yield 2.0 g. It is neutral in reaction and does not give any coloration with FeCl_3 . (Found: C, 74.06; H, 5.41. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 74.02; H, 5.19 per cent). By the action of alcoholic alkalis it gave the acid, m. p. 132° , as described below.

(2) β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)- γ -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-crotonic Acid.—As mentioned above, this acid was obtained on acidification of the alkaline washings of the lactone of m. p. 174° . It could be also obtained from the lactone by the action of alcoholic alkalis.

The above lactone (2 g.) was dissolved in boiling ethyl alcohol and a solution of NaOH (4 g.) in 10 c. c. of water was added. It was heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes, a further quantity of water added, and the alcohol evaporated off. The alkaline filtrate was acidified with HCl (1 N) and the acid obtained could be purified by crystallisation from ethyl alcohol, 50% acetic acid or from water in white, silky needles, m. p. 132° (decomp.). [Found: C, 69.81; H, 5.47; equiv., 327.5. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 69.93; H, 5.22 per cent. Equiv. (monobasic), 326].

The acid is very sensitive towards the action of mineral acids such as HCl , H_2SO_4 , as also acetic anhydride and is converted into the lactone, m. p. 174° .

The acid gives the methyl ester, m. p. 51° (by the silver salt method) and the dark orange pyrylium derivative (m. p. above 300°) is obtained when the acid is treated with salicyl aldehyde in the presence of dry HCl gas.

(3) β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)-propylene-(4-Methoxyphenyl) Ketone.—The above acid (1 g.) was heated slightly above its melting point in an oil-bath, when it decomposed and gave off CO_2 . It was cooled and the solid mass was washed with a small amount of NaHCO_3 solution and then with water. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 97° (Found: C, 76.44; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.61; H, 6.38 per cent).

When oxidised with KMnO_4 by dissolving the ketone in acetone solution, anisic acid was obtained. This ketone gave phenylhydrazone ($\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$), m. p. 126° .

(4) β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)- γ -(4-Methoxybenzoyl)butyric Acid.—The acid of m. p. 132° (1 g.) was dissolved in just sufficient quantity of 0.5N- NaOH solution to which 4% sodium amalgam (10 g.) was slowly added in small portions at a time. The reaction mixture was vigorously shaken for about 45 minutes. After the cessation of evolution of hydrogen, the solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute HCl . The sticky mass was washed with water. After solidification it was powdered and treated with about 2% NaHCO_3 solution (30 c. c.). The filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl and the white precipitate obtained was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m. p. 125° . [Found: C, 69.36; H, 5.97; equiv., 329.4. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 69.5; H, 6.096 per cent. Equiv. (monobasic), 328].

This acid is ketonic in nature and affords a semicarbazone ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3$), m. p. 219° ; a phenylhydrazone ($\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$), m. p. 176° and an oxime ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}$), m. p. 174°

The acid (m.p. 125°) was found identical with an acid obtained by the condensation of β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride with anisole in the presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$. The identity was confirmed by the mixed melting points of the acid as well as of its derivatives.

(5) *Lactone of the β -(methoxyphenyl)- γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)-crotonic acid* was prepared by the same method as described under (1), by using 2.18 g. of the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride, 1.22 g. of *o*-cresol methyl ether, 10 c.c. of nitrobenzene and 3.0 g. of powdered anhydrous $AlCl_3$. The lemon-yellow lactone melts at 176°. (Found: C, 74.25; H, 5.68. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.52; H, 5.59 per cent).

When treated with alcoholic alkali (as in expt. No. 2) it gave the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)- γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-crotonic acid, m.p. 131°. [Found: C, 70.41; H, 5.78; equiv. 340.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.882 per cent. Equiv. (monobasic), 340].

This acid (m.p. 131°) when treated with salicyl aldehyde in the presence of dry HCl gas gave a pyrylium derivative.

When the acid was decarboxylated by heating it above its melting point, it lost CO_2 and gave rise to the ketone, m.p. 84°, $C_{10}H_{20}O_3$, i.e., the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-propylene-(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-ketone. It gave a phenylhydrazone, m.p. 134°.

(6) *The lactone of the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)- γ -(2-methyl-4-methoxy-5-isopropylbenzoyl)-crotonic acid* was prepared by using 2.18 g. of the β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic anhydride, 1.64 g. of thymol methyl ether, 10 c.c. of nitrobenzene and 3 g. of powdered anhydrous $AlCl_3$, by the same method as that described in expt. No. 1. Unlike the lactones described above this lactone is quite colourless in appearance and easily soluble in alcohol, m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 75.73; H, 6.725. $C_{23}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 75.82; H, 6.594 per cent).

β -(4-Methoxyphenyl)- γ -(2-methyl-4-methoxy-5-isopropylbenzoyl)-crotonic Acid.—When treated with 30% solution of NaOH (by dissolving the lactone in alcohol) an acid (m.p. 74°) with an equivalent of 378.2 was obtained. (A monobasic acid with the formula $C_{23}H_{24}O_5$ requires the equivalent 382).

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